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Introduction

Games that are used for acquisition of vocabulary is one of the most crucial step in learning language. When learning a foreign language is one of the most important micro-skills. Below several privileges of games which are utilized in order to teach new vocabulary are given with explanations. The meaning of a game is explained as an activity that is highly stimulating and entertaining, and it can give shy students more opportunity to express their opinion and feelings. They also enable learners to acquire new experiences within a foreign language.

Memory games

Often difference between a successful and unsuccessful language learner has to do with memory. Memory plays a crucial role in learning a new

It is started with one student like chain drill. First student tells one sentence or a phrase relating to the topic and next student will continue it with repeating first sentence or phrase, the most important thing in this period is repeating and using a word or phrase that should be connected to the topic. For example:

1. S: She is an arrogant.
2. S: She is an arrogant and nosey.
3. S: She is an arrogant and nosey but sometimes she is honest...

This game is finished when only one student is left. Memory games is one of the useful games for all aged groups. Especially, with the help of it students can use their brain in effectively.

Crossword puzzle

This game is considered as one of the most famous game that is used in teaching process in order to teach new vocabulary. The most importantly, this is used in order to consolidate new topic. For example, teacher explain new topic "Jobs" after warming up activity new lesson

THE PRIVILEGE OF USING SEVERAL GAMES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING NEW WORDS (AT HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS)

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ABSTRACT

This article is about a wide range of advantageous ways of teaching new vocabulary at higher educational institutions for learners. This article is not only plus sides of using games but also several ways for how to conduct them in the lesson. The most practical ways for teachers in order to teach new vocabulary are given below. Games will be explained with their usage and procedure.

is explained with new words. After teaching new words, teacher divides students into 3 mini groups and gives 3 crossword puzzles. Crossword puzzles not only make easy the process of teaching but also enhance students' ability to memorize words, encourage students' interaction, improve their communicative skills and stimulate students' motivation.

Word games

There is abundance of benefits of playing word games in the classroom and they are notable. With the help of Word game, you can increase vocabulary. It means that richer one's vocabulary is, the easier it becomes to organize and express thoughts and opinions as well as interpreting and understanding what others are saying and the world in general. Learning can be active or passive in these games. Except from above mentioned factors, it improves spelling. Not knowing how to correctly spell a word is the same as not knowing the word at all. Both it enhances cognitive skills and it promotes a self-improving competition. Students can recharge their batteries as well. All word games can help relieve stress. While getting immersed in the letters and words, students can shut off negative thoughts and forget about their problems for an instant.

Topic discussion

The students will choose a discussion topic (climate, family, relationship, animals). Then teacher divide students into groups. Then the group is divided into two teams. The students of each team should give sentences turn by turn. Students should use emphatic construction "it is ...that" .Then winner will tell last sentence. Students' should use their imaginations also. They will use a wide range of vocabulary. Students will recharge their batteries.

Team game

Students will be divided into two groups. Teacher should prepare cards beforehand and put cards on the table and students will choose cards . First students will choose and tell it's country. Another group will tell it's language or languages. After finishing first group , then students will change their turns. Team games will create friendly atmosphere between students. It enhance understanding each other.

Conclusion:

Taking all into consideration, learning a language takes a lot of effort. Games assist students in making and maintaining the effort required for learning. Vocabulary acquisition is increasingly viewed as crucial to language acquisition. Moreover, learning vocabulary is often perceived as a tedious and laborious process. Memory games, Crossword puzzle, Word games.

References:

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